

Research Article

Molecular Analysis of G1691A Mutation in Factor 5 Leiden and its relation with mtDNA common deletion in Human Recurrent Pregnancy Loss

Negin Garoosi¹, Hussein Rasi*² and Mahdi Goudarzi³

¹Department of Biology,

Karaj branch, Islamic Azad University, Karaj, Iran

²Department of Biology,

Karaj branch, Islamic Azad University, Karaj, Iran

³Department of Physiology and Pharmacology, School of Medicine,

Alborz University of Medical Sciences, Karaj, Iran.

*Correspondence Author: rasihussein@yahoo.com

[Received 12 Aug-2020, Modified May-2021, Accepted 02 Jan-2022, Published 19 Jan-2022]

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6283539

ABSTRACT:

Background: In general, miscarriage is one of the most common complications of pregnancy and it is the pregnancy loss before 20 weeks of gestation or birth weight below 500 grams. Recurrent Pregnancy Loss is defined as two or more spontaneous miscarriages. Genetic disorders such as mutations can be involved in miscarriage. Considering the importance of this issue, in this study, G1691A mutation of coagulation factor 5 and common deletion mutation in the mitochondrial genome (4977-bp deletion in mtDNA) were investigated as factors which can influence miscarriage, especially recurrent miscarriage.

Materials and Methods: For this study 41 patients with the history of miscarriage and 48 healthy women with successful delivery were selected and completed the questionnaires which included questions such as miscarriage history, age, blood type and then Blood samples were taken. After extraction of DNA from each sample, the studied mutations were determined using PCR method. At the end, analysis of the results and assessment of other important and effective factors in them was done using Epi Info software and using chi square (X^2) test.

Results: Among the patients, there were 29.25% patients with one miscarriage, 65.85% patients with two miscarriages and 4.9% patients with three miscarriages. There was no homozygous genotype in the study of G1691A mutations in both groups, and prevalence of heterozygotes was 17% among patients and 4.17% among controls. On the other hand, frequency of 4977-bp deletion in mtDNA in patients group and control group was 68.29% and 14.58%, respectively. Analysis showed that frequency of G1691A mutations and common deletion mutation in mtDNA in patients group were higher than controls and were statistically significant. Although the opportunity to have miscarriage in GA genotype and carriers of common deletion is more than control, but there is not any correlation between these two mutations and their inheritability and also they have not affected each other. Therefore, we can use the above mutations as a molecular marker for early detection and timely treatment in patient's likelihood of miscarriage.

Keywords: G1691A, Factor 5 Leiden, common deletion in mtDNA, recurrent miscarriage

INTRODUCTION

Miscarriage is one of the most common problems in pregnancy and includes about 15% to 25% of all diagnosed pregnancies. Recurrent

pregnancy loss is also a type of miscarriage defined as two or more clinical pregnancy loss before 20 weeks of pregnancy and affects

approximately 1% to 5% of women of reproductive age all over the world based on the number (1-2-3-27-28). Although various factors have known that are effective in recurrent pregnancy loss (due to its multi-factorial nature) like genetic disorders (including abnormal number of chromosomes, chromosome structural abnormalities and mutations), immunological, endocrine and anatomic disorders, infectious agents, environmental factors, lifestyle, age, thrombophilia and oxidative stress,...,but in half the time reasons remain unknown (2-10-28). Among these mentioned factors, 2% to 5% of miscarriages are due to genetic abnormalities like mutations (2). One of the important mutation is the G1691A mutation in Coagulation Factor 5 (factor 5 Leiden) which have particular importance in the creation of thrombophilia. One of the other important mutations, is the common deletion mutation in mitochondrial DNA which cause 4977-bp deletion in mtDNA and increase possibility of occurrence in mitochondria in case of mitochondrial oxidative stress (as a center for the production of free radicals of oxidative stress). G1691A point mutations in Coagulation Factor 5 known as Factor 5 Leiden. In this mutation, Factor 5 is resistance to break down and remains active for a longer time that is associated with an increased risk of thrombosis, and then aberrant blood clot or thrombus build in the capillaries of the placenta can cause confusion in the exchange of substances between mother and fetus ultimately results in miscarriage (5-9-19-21-22). Hussein Najmabadi et al (2009) examined the genetic Factor 5 Leiden which create thrombophilia, as a genetic factor for cardiovascular disease and there was no mutation of Factor 5 Leiden as homozygous and the frequency of G1691A mutation all over Iran was 2.4% in average with different rates in different ethnicities(3). Karim Shams Asanjani et al (2013) studied genetic mutation in Coagulation Factor 5 gene in the normal population of Eastern Azerbaijan province in order to be effective in prognosis of thrombotic disorders, cardiovascular disease, RSA, etc. and

declared the allelic frequencies in the population (4). Oztork Nesrin et al (2014) in another study studied Coagulation Factor 5 mutation in 201 patients and found that the presence of allele A in G1691A mutation as heterozygous increases the possibility of venous thrombosis (blood clot in the vein) (5). Ashraf Moeini et al (2010) investigated thrombophilia factors association with pregnancy complications in women with polycystic ovary. The results show that there is a significant statistical difference between women with polycystic ovary syndrome and healthy women in term of pregnancy complications records but there is no significant difference in terms of Thrombophilia factors (Factor 5 Leiden) and the relationship between these factors with pregnancy complications records between those two groups (6). Wasim Almawi et al (2002) investigated the prevalence of G1691A mutation in the Factor 5 gene and G20210A mutation in Factor 2 gene in women with recurrent pregnancy loss and it was found that the prevalence of both mutations is several times higher in patients with recurrent pregnancy loss than the control population (8). A study by Cornelia Wolf et al. (2003) investigated the recurrent pregnancy loss and its relationship with the G1691A mutation in the Factor 5 gene, G20210A mutation in Factor 2 gene and mutation in plasminogen gene inhibitors- activator, and the results showed that G1691A mutation in the Factor 5 gene was more prevalent in patients with recurrent pregnancy loss (9). common deletion mutation in the mitochondrial DNA, is important in many diseases, too. A study by Zivar Salehi et al(2013), expressed that there is a correlation between common deletion mutation in mtDNA and peptic ulcer(23). Zahiri et al(2013) studied the common deletion mutation in mtDNA in women with spontaneous miscarriage and they saw the increase risk of spontaneous miscarriage with this mutation (14). So, the current study examines the prevalence of mutations in the coagulation factor 5 (factor 5 Leiden) and the prevalence of common deletion mutation in the mitochondrial genome and if there are, the relationship between these two

mutations, as well as review some important affecting factors, so that if possible to determine the prevalence and the factors affecting it help in early detection and early treatment of patients prone to be involved in abortion.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research was a kind of case-control study. 41 patients with the history of miscarriage and 48 healthy women with successful delivery were studied after completed the questionnaires. In

Table 1. The sequence of primers used in the identification of G1691A mutations in Factor 5 Leiden

Mutation	sequence of primers	PCR product
FV G1691A	(C): 5'-GGA CTA CTT GAC AAT TAC TGT TCT CTT G-3' (N): 5'-GCA GAT CCC TGG ACA GAC G-3' (M): 5'-GCA GAT CCC TGG ACA GAC A-3'	150 bp

this study, blood samples were taken ,then Extraction of DNA was done by Salting Out method using Cinnagen kit (DN8115C) and were used separately to examine both mutations.

PCR reactions for G1691A mutations in Factor 5

After extraction of DNA ,PCR reaction was performed to detect G1691A mutation in Factor 5 Leiden using Cinnagen kit (PR8251C) and specific primers for this mutation according to the following protocol

Table 2. PCR Materials required for G1691A mutations in Factor 5

Materials	Quantities
Master Mix	12/5µl
Forward Primer	1µl
Reverse Primer	1µl
Distilled water	7µl
DNA	3/5µl
Total Volume	25µl

Table 3. PCR thermal cycles for G1691A mutation in Factor 5

Step	Temperature	Incubation Time	Number of cycle
First Denaturation	95°C	10 min	1
Denaturation	94°C	30 sec	10
Annealing	60°C	30 sec	
Extension	72°C	1min	
Denaturation	94°C	30 sec	25
Annealing	55°C	30 sec	
Extension	72°C	1min	
Final Extension	72°C	5min	1

PCR reaction for 4977 bp mutation (common deletion) in mtDNA

PCR reaction was performed to detect common deletion in mtDNA using Cinnagen kit (PR8251C) and specific primers for this mutation according to Cinnagen protocol.

Table. The sequence of primers used in the identification of common deletion in mtDNA

Mutation	Primer sequences	Product PCR
MtDNA1	5'-TTC-TCC-TAG-ACC-TAA-CCT-GA-3'	485bp
MtDNA2	5'-GGA-TAT-ACT-ACA-GCG-ATG-GC-3'	485bp
MtDNA3	5'-TGT-GGT-CTT-TGG-AGT-AGA-AAC-C-3'	127bp
MtDNA4	5'- CCT-TAC-ACT-ATT-CCT-CAT-CAC-C-3'	127bp

Table 5. PCR Materials required for common deletion mutation in mtDNA

PCR Master Mix	13.0µl
Primer Forward	2.0µl
Primer Reverse	2.0µl
DNA Template	3µg
dH2O	5.0µl

Table 6. PCR thermal cycles for common deletion mutation in mtDNA

Step	Temperature	Incubation Time	Number of cycle
Pre-PCR heat step	95°C	10min	1 Cyc
Denatuation	95°C	30s	35Cyc
Annealing	60°C	30s	
Extension	72°C	45s	

Then, specimens were loaded on the agarose gel(1%) and after electrophoresing, they were observed by UV Transbillimator and evaluated.

Statistical analysis

Epi Info software version 7.1.3.10 and Chi-Square test (χ^2) were used to analyze the data.

RESULTS

All members of two groups were investigated and then results were classified .

Patients classification based on the number of miscarriages

Frequency of miscarriage samples in patients group is presented in table 7. There were 29/25% patients with sporadic pregnancy loss, 65/85% with two and 4/9% with three pregnancy losses

Table 7. Classification of patients based on the number of miscarriage

Number of miscarriage	Number of patients	Percentage
Once	12	29.25%
Twice	27	65.85%
Three times	2	4.9%

Patients classification based on the age

A total of four age groups were determined. According to the survey, the lowest number of miscarriages was in the age group below 20 years with a frequency of 17.07% and the highest number of miscarriages was in patients older than 31 years with a frequency of 36.58%.

Table 8. Classification of patients based on age

Percentage	No.	Age group
17.07%	7	Below20
21.95%	9	21-25
24.39%	10	26-30
36.58%	15	Over 31

Patients classification based on the blood type

The results of patients classification based on the blood type are shown in Table (9). The most frequent blood type is O positive blood type (36.58%) and AB negative was not observed among individuals.

Table 9. Classification of patients based on blood type

Percentage	No.	blood type
17.1%	7	A ⁺
7.3%	3	A ⁻
9.75%	4	B ⁺
7.3%	3	B ⁻
4.87%	2	AB ⁺
0%	0	AB ⁻
36.58%	15	O ⁺
17.1%	7	O ⁻

Patients classification based on the consanguinity

In the survey, there were 8 incidents of consanguineous marriages in patient groups and 2 cases in controls. Therefore, statistical analysis shows a significant difference in two groups of patients and controls in terms of marriage and parental consanguinity has increased miscarriage rate.

Table 10. Classification of patients based on consanguinity marriage

Percentage	No.	Consanguinity marriage
19.5%	8	Patients
4.16%	2	Non- patients

($X^2=5.22$, $P<0.05$)

Patients classification based on the family history of miscarriage

There were 10 cases of miscarriages (parents or siblings) in close relatives in the study group, and 4 cases of miscarriages in the control group. Based on statistical analysis carried out there was a significant difference between cases and controls regarding the family history of miscarriage and the family history of miscarriage increases the likelihood of miscarriage.

Table 11. Classification of patients based on the family history of miscarriage

the family history of miscarriage	No.	Percentage
Patients	10	24.3%
Non- patients	4	8.33%

($X^2=4.30$, $P<0.05$)

The frequency of G1691A mutation in coagulation factor 5 in the groups studied

The frequency of G1691A mutation in coagulation Factor 5 heterozygous was 17% in the patients group and 4.17% for the control group. homozygous mutation was not observed in the studied populations.

Table 12. The G1691A mutation frequency in the coagulation Factor 5 in sample groups

Genotype	Patient		Control	
	No.	Percentage	No.	Percentage
GG	34	82.93%	46	95.83%
GA	7	17.07%	2	4.17%
AA	0	0	0	0

Analysis of the frequency of GG and GA genotype in two groups of patients and controls were statistically significant ($p\leq 0.05$) and the likelihood of miscarriage for genotypes GA is about three times higher than the control group.

Figure 1. The results of electrophoresis of PCR products for the detection of G1691A mutation in coagulation factor 5

In the figure, Lane M- 100 bp is molecular marker, lanes 1, 2 are for negative control specimens of normal and mutant type, lanes 3,4, 5 are normal type specimens and lanes 6-7 -8 are mutants specimens.

Frequency of patients with G1691A mutation in different age ranges

In this classification, the maximum heterozygous patients was for the Group over 31 years with a frequency of 60% but statistical analysis shows that there is no significant relationship between G1691A mutations and age.

Table 13. Frequency of patients with G1691A mutation in different age ranges

Percentage	No.	Age group
20%	1	Below20
20%	1	21-25
0	0	26-30
60%	3	Over 31

Prevalence and statistical analysis of common deletion in mtDNA in the groups studied

In examining the presence or absence of common remove mutations upon the mitochondrial genome we observed that 68.29% of patients and 14.58% of control group had the mutation. Statistical analysis of the frequency of common deletion in mtDNA in both patients and controls was significant ($p < 0.01$) and the risk of miscarriage for patients with this mutation are more than control group.

Table 14. The frequency of common deletion in mtDNA

Controls(No., percentage)		patients(No., percentage)		the presence or absence of common remove mutations
absence of mutation	presence of mutation	absence of mutation	presence of mutation	
41 (85.42%)	7(14.58%)	13 (31.71%)	28 (68.29%)	

Figure 2. Electrophoresis of PCR products for the detection of common deletion in mtDNA

According to the figure, the bold bands close to 500 bp are 485 bp normal types and band close to 100 bp is common mutation band size 127 bp. Lane M, molecular marker sized 100 bp, lanes 1, 3, 4, 5 and 6 have common deletion in mtDNA with 127 bp band and normal type of 485 bp. Specimen No. 8 has no common deletion but has normal band, but specimens No. 2 and 7 are negative control samples where the DNA is replaced by distilled water.

Frequency of patients with common deletion in mtDNA in different age ranges

In this classification the most frequent age group which has the mutation, was over 30 years with the frequency of 50%. Statistical analysis ($p < 0.01$) showed that common deletion in mtDNA occurrence and increasing age were significant, so that as age increases, the

likelihood of common deletion in mtDNA increases.

Table 15. Frequency of patients with common deletion in mtDNA in different age ranges

Patients (No. and percentage)	Age group
1 (3.5%)	Below20
6 (21.5%)	21-25
7 (25%)	26-30
14 (50%)	Over 31

The relationship between factor V Leiden and common deletion in mtDNA

The statistical analysis shows that there is no significant correlation between the frequency of G1691A mutation in coagulation factor 5 and common deletion mutation in mitochondria genome. This means that both mutations produce no effect on each other, but independently effective on miscarriage.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Miscarriage is one of the main problems of pregnancy and Recurrent pregnancy loss (RPL) is one of the most common types of spontaneous miscarriage. So far, several factors such as genetic, hormonal and anatomical disorders, oxidative stress, and environmental factors have been identified that can be regarded as the exact cause of recurrent miscarriage. Genetic disorders are important in RPL and may also be effective in idiopathic miscarriage, like mutations in different genes. From these mutations we can name mutations in the coagulation factors and mutations in the mitochondrial genome. The current paper studied mutations in blood coagulation Factor 5 (Factor 5 Leiden) and common deletion mutation in the mitochondrial genome. Factor 5's G1691A mutation causes a defect in coagulation pathway causing a misplaced blood clot or thrombus within the blood and since fetal health has direct contact with the maternal circulation any factor disruptive in this respect is detrimental to the fetus (20-21). There are many researches in regard to G1691A mutation and Factor 5 Leiden. There are many studies that have introduced the mutation as a risk factor for recurrent miscarriage. While there are other reports that rejected the relationship between the mutations and recurrent miscarriage. In fact, the differences in the studies could be related to differences in the number of cases and also differences in inclusion criteria. The current study found significant relationship between G1691A mutations in Factor 5 (Factor 5 Leiden) and recurrent miscarriage in both groups of patients and control indicates approximately 3 times higher risk of miscarriage at the presence of this mutation. Rai et al (2001) studied women with RPL and found no increase in G1691A mutation compared to the control group (13). In another study by Rai et al (2006) three common mutations in thrombophilia factor 5 Leiden include mutations (G1691A) prothrombin (G20210A), and MATHFR (C677T) reviewed and confirmed that both patient group and the control group show the same frequency of

mutations but simultaneous mutations in the patient group that increases the likelihood of recurrent pregnancy loss (11). On the other hand the results of the current study show (17%) prevalence of genotype heterozygous GA in the patients group and (4.7%) in the control group that is less compared to another study conducted by Behjati et al (2006) in an Iranian population with the 20% frequency of mutations in the patient population (13). In the study conducted by Behjati mutation was absent in the control group and generally in both studies G1691A mutation prevalence was higher in the patient group with significant difference between G1691A mutations and recurrent pregnancy loss in the two groups (7). These results are consistent with that of Wolf et al (2003) which showed a 10% frequency of factor 5 Leiden in patients with recurrent miscarriage and 19% frequency of factor 5 Leiden in infertility patients, compared with the control (9). In another study by Glueck et al (2005), the higher incidence of Factor 5 Leiden in women with recurrent spontaneous miscarriage was reported (16) and the results are consistent with that of Glueck prior research in 2003 that, 19% patients with recurrent spontaneous miscarriage showed factor 5 Leiden mutation while only 6% group of control showed mutations (17). In another report (2008), 21.5% of patients were with Factor 5 Leiden and only 7.4% of the control group were eligible for this mutation (12). It seems homozygous lethal in the mutations that can inhibit correct angiogenesis in placenta that causes early miscarriage of the fetus two or three weeks after fertilization. In this study, homozygous genotype was not observed in any of the study groups while the research carried out by Almawi et al (2002) as the prevalence of G1691A mutations in Factor 5 and G20210A mutation in Factor 2 in patients with recurrent pregnancy loss was found as mutant homozygote with the frequency of 15.55% in patients, as well as heterozygous G1691A mutation frequency of 40.91% in patients and 16.42% in the control group, respectively. (8) On the other hand, there are reports about the association between

homozygosity for this mutation and IVF failure (15). Common deletion mutation in mtDNA cause 4799 bp deletion in mtDNA and is one of the most important changes in the mitochondrial genome, which is acclaimed an interfere with the early stages of embryonic development before implantation, and miscarriage in the early stages. The role of oxidative stress and free radicals that cause mutations in the mitochondrial genome in various diseases has been investigated in recent years. (14-23-25). In the current study, the frequency of common deletion mutation was determined 68.29% and 14.58% in patients group and controls, respectively. The frequency of common deletion mutation in the mitochondrial genome in both groups of patients and control was statistically significant and chances for people with mitochondrial common deletion mutation for miscarriage is more than 10 times compared to the control group. This is somehow consistent with the results of Zahiri et al (2013) with the subject of “study of common deletion mutation in the mitochondrial genome of women with spontaneous miscarriage”, which showed the 30% and 6.66% prevalence of common deletion mutation in patients and controls, respectively, with a relationship between the increased risk of spontaneous miscarriage.(14) A study by Sumitha et al (2015) at the age group of 21 to 45 years revealed that oxidative stress and damage to nuclear DNA and mitochondrial DNA in patients with recurrent pregnancy loss increases with age that is consistent with our results indicating the prevalence of mutations with increased age (18). Generally, it can be concluded that the frequency of coagulation Factor 5 G1691A mutation and mitochondrial common deletion mutation were statistically significant and of in both groups of patients and controls with the several times higher risk of miscarriage in GA genotypes and carriers with a chance for common deletion mutation in mitochondrial DNA. However, there are no significant relationship between miscarriage and inheritance in terms of both mutations. But given the high incidence of it in RPL, the two above-mentioned mutations can be used as a

molecular marker for early detection of individuals prone to miscarriage and timely treatment.

REFERENCES

1. Williams Obstetrics (Cunningham, Kenneth Leveno, Gill Strip, Huth, Westermann) 2010
2. Kashanyan M., Akbarian A., Shbandvst Sh., “The effects of one occurrence of spontaneous miscarriage pregnancy on the next pregnancy”, Iran University of Medical Sciences, 2004, 463 Vol. XI, No. 41
3. Najmb Abadi H., Imanian H., Hadavi V., Kariminejad A., Rostami M., Abrokaniz K., “genetic study of factor 5 Leiden polymorphisms as genetic factor of cardiovascular disease in Iran population”, genetic the third millennium, winter, 2009,7 (4): 1844-1847
4. Shams Asanjan K., Pourakbar A., Farsh Dosti Haqi M., Karimiyan Fathi N., “Coagulation Factor 5 gene G1691A mutation in the normal population of East Azerbaijan province, Urmia Medical Journal, June 2013,24 (3): 219- 225
5. Ozturk ErÇelen N., Öztürk B., Cömert H., Diken M., Gültomruk M., Coşkun H., Akat A., Allelic Frequencies of Mutations in Blood Coagulation Factor Genes (Factor V, Factor II) and Methylenetetrahydrofolate Reductase (MTHFR) in 201 Turkish Patients with Venous Thrombosis Complications; J Mol Genet Med, 2014;8:1
6. Moeini A., Sarrafiun F., Ziyae S., Faghihzadeh S., “The relationship between thrombophilia factors and pregnancy complications in Pcos women”, bimonthly Journal of Shahed University, July 2010, Issue 87
7. Behjati R., Modarressi M., Jeddi- Tehrani M., Dokoohaki P., Ghasemi J., Zarnani AH., Thrombophilic mutations in Iranian patient with infertility and recurrent spontaneous abortion. Ann Hematol 2006, 85 (4): 268-71
8. Almawi W., Finan R., Tamim H., Ameen G., Sharida H., Rashid M., Prevalence of factor V G1691A (Factor V-Leiden) and

- Prothrombin G20210A Gene Mutations in a Recurrent Miscarriage Population, *American Journal of Hematology*, 2002 ; 71:300-305.
9. Wolf C., Haubelt H., Ulrich Pauer H., Hinney B., Krome-Cesar C., Legler T., Hellstern P., Emons G., Zoll B., Köhler M., Recurrent pregnancy loss and Relation to FV Leiden, FII G20210A and Polymorphisms of Plasminogen Activator and Plasminogen Activator Inhibitor, *Pathophysiol Haemost Thromb*, 2003; 33:134-137.
 10. Hizem S., Almawi W., Finan R., Tamim H., Mahjoub T., Mtraoui N., Nsiri B., Association between adverse pregnancy outcomes and maternal factor V G1691A (Leiden) and Prothrombin G20210A genotypes in women with a history of recurrent idiopathic miscarriages, *American Journal of Hematology*, 2005; 80:12-19
 11. Rai R., Jivraj S., Underwood J., Regan L., Genetic thrombophilic mutations among couples with recurrent miscarriage, *Human Reproduction*, 2006; 21(5), 1161-1165.
 12. Glueck C., Gogenini S., Munjal J., Tracy T., Pranikoff J., Wang P., Factor V Leiden mutation: a treatable etiology for sporadic and recurrent pregnancy loss, *Fertil Steril* 2008 Feb; 89:410-416.
 13. Rai R., Shlabak A., Cohen H., Backos M., Holmes Z., Marriott K., Regan L., Factor V Leiden and acquired activated protein C resistance among 1000 women with recurrent miscarriage, *Hum Reprod* 2001; 16(5): 961-5
 14. Zahiri Sarvari, Z., Askafi Sabet, Salehi Z., Ghanami., Gashti N., "To study of bp- 4977 deletion in mitochondrial DNA in women with spontaneous miscarriage", *Journal of Gilan University of Medical Sciences*, January 2013, Issue twenty-second, No. 88, p. 1-6
 15. Azem F., Many A., Ben Ami I., Yovel I., Amit A., Lessing J., Increased rates of thrombophilia in women with repeated IVF failures. *Hum Reprod* 2004; 19(2): 368-70.
 16. Glueck C., Pranikoff J., Aregawi D., Haque M., Zhu B., Tracy T., Wang P., The factor V Leiden mutation, high factor VIII, and high plasminogen activator inhibitor activity: etiologies for sporadic miscarriage, *Metabolism*, 2005 ; 54(10) 1345-9
 17. Glueck C., Wang P., Bornovali S., Goldenberg N., Sieve L., Polycystic ovary syndrome, The G1691A factor V Leiden mutation, and plasminogen activator inhibitor activity: association with recurrent pregnancy loss, *Metabolism* 2003; 52 (12) 1627-32
 18. Sumitha Prabhu P., Aneesh P., Jiju J., Reshma P., Dinesh Roy D., Evidence of increased oxidative stress and DNA damages in women with recurrent miscarriages, *International Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research*, 2015 May; 6(5)
 19. Zoosmann-Diskin A., Gazit B., Peleg L., Shohat M., Turner D., Thrombophilic polymorphisms in Israel, *Blood Cells Mol Dis* 2008; 41:230-3
 20. Silver Robert M., Fetal Death, *Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 2007 Jan; 109(1)
 21. Stief Thomas W., Single oxygen inactivates fibrinogen, factor V, factor VIII, factor X and platelet aggregation of human blood, *Thrombosis research* 2000; 97(6):473-480
 22. Zammiti W., Miraoui N., Mrcier E., Abboud N., Saidi S., Mahjoub T., Almawi W., Gris J., Association of factor V gene polymorphism (Leiden, Cambridge, Hong Kong and HR2 haplotype) with recurrent idiopathic pregnancy loss in Tunisia. *Thromb Haemost*, 2006; 95(4):612-7
 23. Salehi Z., Haghghi A., Fakhrie Asl S., Aminian K., Investigate prevalence of 4977bp deletion in mitochondrial DNA in patients with peptic ulcer, *Birjand Medical Journal*, 2013, 21 (1): 48-55
 24. Teede H., Deeks A., Moran L., Polycystic ovary syndrome: a complex condition with psychological, reproductive and metabolic manifestations that impacts on health across the lifespan, *BMC Med* 2010; 8:41
 25. Thayer R., Wittcock R., Parr R., Zullo S., Birch-Machin M., A maternal line study investigating the 4977-bp mitochondrial DNA deletion, *Experimental Gerontology* 38, 2003; 567-571

26. Malini S., Chaithra P., Kumar C., An Overview of Genetic and Molecular Factors Responsible for Recurrent Pregnancy Loss, *Int Hum Genet*, 2011; 11(4): 217-225
27. M. Abou-Gabal K., El-Fayoumi H., El-Shabrawy E., Amani H., Roshdi A., Prevalence and Causes of Recurrent Abortion among Women in Beni-Suef Governorate, *Life Science Journal* 2013; 10(3)
28. Vanniarajan A., Govindaraj P., Carlus S., Aruna M., Aruna P., Kumar A., Jayakar R., Lionel A., Gupta S., Rao L., Gupta N., Chakravarthy B., Deenadayal M., Selvaraj K., Andal S., Reddy B., Singh L., Thangaraj K., Mitochondrial DNA variations associated with recurrent pregnancy loss among Indian women, *Mitochondrion*, 2011; 10: 1016.